

AN IMPORTANT ROLE OF USING FLASHCARDS DURING THE TEACHING OF VOCABULARY

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to evaluate the effects of using flashcard media for teaching vocabulary and identify the teachers' responses towards the use of flashcard media for teaching foreign languages. Using flashcards to teach the students in an interesting way.

The effective methods of teaching students using flashcards and interactive games are explained in the article.

Vocabulary has a great place and role during teaching because we can first learn the language through this and understand the meaning that comes from it. If our knowledge of grammar is strong but our vocabulary is weak, we will not succeed. The wealth of vocabulary is in the 1st place in learning a language in any direction. We rely on vocabulary in listening, writing, reading, and of course, speaking. If we don't have enough vocabulary, we can't speak, hear, understand, write, or read. Therefore, vocabulary is given great importance in teaching language to schoolchildren, starting from school age. In such cases, flashcards are our current most effective and modern method. Flashcards are one of the media usually used by teachers. Flashcards were first used in the 19th century by English educational theorist Favel Lee Mortimer. Mortimer used flashcards to help teach literacy. Currently, there are various options for using flash cards. Most of them are based on interval repetition of the material.

I use flashcards with many language learning techniques and it will definitely help the students to develop and learn the language quickly. One of these methods is to work with flashcards on a theme and add them to different games to make them more memorable and interesting for the student, that is, to run the flash card and the game at the same time in the same order. For example, we can use the flower method to make it more interesting. In this method, students need water in a glass, paper flowers, and flashcards with words written on them. Numbers are written inside the paper flowers, and these numbers determine which number of flashcards will be taken by the reader. In this, the student chooses a flower with closed leaves and drops it upright into the water in the glass, and the flower opens in the

glass, and then he determines the number of the flash card he needs to answer by the number written on the flower and answers the flash card with the number that fell. A student who is unable to answer a question or a word on a flashcard fulfills a condition written on the back of the flash card, for example, the conditions of the punishment method are written there as a joke. For example, there are conditions such as doing 10 sit-ups or saying 10 times fast in one breath.

The next interesting activity is called "Basketball". In this activity, vocabulary is written on flashcards, and students are divided into 2 groups and stand in a standing position. The teacher shows the notes on the flashcards one by one. Then whichever team finds the word first, write it on a piece of paper with their team's name on it and crumples it into a round ball, like a basketball. Then they throw it into the basket in front of the teacher and the game continues in this way. In the end, the team that finds the most words and manages to put them in the basket wins the game. Through this game, students will also test their knowledge and learn new words, and this game will increase their hunting ability and interest in the lesson. Action games definitely give students a unique impression and great fun. This ensures that the lessons are more effective and modern.

The use of such methods firstly increases the student's interest in the lesson, and secondly, through this method, we strengthen our mind and knowledge and remember the words, and in addition, we can raise our mood by performing two or three different actions. It can be a really helpful method for every single pupil. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to the conditions for mastering the mother tongue. The main goal of the method is the idea that you can learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language. The most important and most effective of the natural method and the principles included in it is the creation of a language environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of advanced methodical principles. This branch of linguistics interprets language not as a system of linguistic forms, but as a field of human activity. In the field of foreign language education, since the beginning of the 70s, a new set of conclusions has caused intense discussions in the field of setting educational goals. New curricula have been adopted that determine the main directions of foreign language education, with the goal of "teaching students to communicate", we cannot learn any foreign language without a deep study of its methodology. The method of "communicative didactics" is also considered important in the methodology of foreign language teaching. Communicative didactics include the following. Through these games, students will also test their knowledge and learn new words, and this game will increase their hunting ability and interest in the lesson. Action games definitely give students a unique impression and great fun. This ensures that the lessons are more effective and modern.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted science in which a person experiences complex psychological changes. Using modern pedagogical technologies, teaching a foreign language in comparison with the mother tongue gives effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology and, of course, a larger vocabulary.

Effective methods and modern technologies are important in the process of learning and teaching a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are the communicative didactic

method, intercultural dialogue organization method, and exercise organization method. All three methods are closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created. Flashcards are effective teaching media that could apply to teaching vocabulary to young learners in their classroom. During the process of teaching the teachers must be able to use flashcards effectively and it is needed teachers creativity to design interesting flashcards. The colors sizes and shapes. Flashcards have an impact on students' ability to receive vocabulary in the learning process and increased the classroom atmosphere because the students were more enthusiastic. By using the flashcard, the students were enthusiastic and can be managed because they were focused on the teacher when the teacher showed flashcards to them while mentioning the name of the picture of it. So the using of flashcards can be more effective than others to learn and remember more things.

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